

1 **Habitat suitability and distribution of harbour and grey seals in the Baltic Sea region**

2 Anders Galatius^{1*}, Jonas Teilmann¹, Markus P. Ahola^{2,3}, Anja M. Carlsson², Rune Dietz¹,
3 Carla Freitas⁴, Inari Helle⁵, Ivar Jüssi⁶, Mart Jüssi^{6,7}, Mervi Kunasranta^{8,9}, Morten Tange
4 Olsen^{1,10}, Jacob Carstensen¹, Floris M. van Beest^{1*}

5 ¹Marine Mammal Research, Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej
6 399, DK-4000 Roskilde, Denmark

7 ²Department of Population Analysis and Monitoring, Swedish Museum of Natural History, S-
8 10405 Stockholm, Sweden

9 ³Marine Environment Research Group, Turku University of Applied Sciences, FI-20520
10 Turku, Finland

11 ⁴Institute of Marine Research, Flødevigen Research Station, 4817 His, Norway

12 ⁵Natural Resources Institute Finland, FI-00790 Helsinki, Finland

13 ⁶Pro Mare, Vintriku, EE-75121 Kose, Estonia

14 ⁷Institute of Ecology and Earth Sciences, University of Tartu, EE-50409 Tartu, Estonia

15 ⁸University of Eastern Finland, Department of Environmental and Biological Sciences, FI-
16 80100 Joensuu, Finland

17 ⁹Natural Resources Institute Finland, FI-80100 Joensuu, Finland¹⁰Section for Molecular
18 Ecology and Evolution, Globe Institute, University of Copenhagen, DK-1353 Copenhagen K,
19 Denmark

20 *Corresponding authors: Anders Galatius, agj@ecos.au.dk, Floris M. van Beest,

21 flbe@ecos.au.dk

22 Running head: *Distribution of grey and harbour seals in the Baltic*

23 **Abstract**

24 The Baltic Sea region is impacted by pollution, noise, offshore constructions, shipping,
25 fisheries, eutrophication and climate change. Seals are important top predators here, but little

26 is known about their at-sea distribution. Using satellite telemetry data from 90 harbour seals
27 (*Phoca vitulina*) and 65 grey seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) together with haulout counts, we
28 model habitat suitability and relative population densities across the region. We use
29 generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs), incorporating a range of static and dynamic
30 environmental variables. Habitat suitability of both species was positively related to
31 proximity to haulouts, explaining 25-30% of the total deviance. Other important variables,
32 explaining 2.5-6% of the deviance in habitat suitability, were increased wave exposure and
33 colder sea surface temperature for harbour seals and for grey seals wave exposure and higher
34 sea bottom oxygen saturation. Harbour seals had preference for more coastal habitats than
35 grey seals. The analyses show imbalance between habitat suitability and actual distribution,
36 particularly for grey seals, where some areas with high suitability had low seal densities. This
37 likely reflects the dramatic population fluctuations of seals in the area over recent centuries
38 related to hunting and pollution. Overlap of suitable habitats between the species in the
39 southern and western Baltic indicates interspecific competition that will likely increase as
40 grey seals recolonise their previous range. Our study constitutes the first comprehensive
41 analysis of seal distribution in the Baltic area and is a valuable tool for managers and
42 ecologists assessing pressures and ecosystem interactions in an area where anthropogenic
43 activities are increasing.

44

45 **Keywords:**

46 Central place forager, density maps, interspecific competition, pinniped, species distribution
47 model (SDM), satellite tracking, *Phoca vitulina*, *Halichoerus grypus*

48

49 1. Introduction

50 Coastal marine habitats around the world are affected by pollution (Sonne et al. 2020),
51 offshore construction and shipping (Duarte et al. 2021), fisheries (Jackson et al. 2001),
52 eutrophication (Maúre et al. 2021) and climate change (Meier et al. 2022). Marine apex
53 predators are often used as indicators for ecosystem health as they are affected by changes at
54 lower trophic levels and shape ecosystems by top-down regulation (Moore 2008, Hazen et al.
55 2019). Their distribution provides valuable information regarding interactions with other
56 ecosystem components in time and space.

57 Four marine mammals inhabit the Baltic Sea ecosystem: harbour porpoise (*Phocoena*
58 *phocoena*), ringed seal (*Pusa hispida*), harbour seal (*Phoca vitulina*) and grey seal
59 (*Halichoerus grypus*). The semi-enclosed nature of the Baltic Sea means that pollutants and
60 other anthropogenic impacts accumulate, leading to drastic environmental effects (Reusch et
61 al. 2018). In line with this, all marine mammal species have undergone substantial declines in
62 abundance due to overhunting, reproductive deficiencies caused by pollutants, bycatch in
63 fishery, overfishing and eutrophication leading to food web disruption in the past century
64 (Heide-Jørgensen & Härkönen 1988, Harding & Härkönen 1999, Kokko et al. 1999,
65 HELCOM 2009, Olsen et al. 2018).

66 At-sea distribution of marine predators is heavily impacted by prey distribution (Benoit-Bird
67 et al. 2013, Bennington et al. 2020). Both grey and harbour seals are piscivores and
68 opportunistic foragers, adapting their diet to locally and temporarily available species
69 (Wilson & Hammond 2015, Scharff-Olsen et al. 2018, Kappa et al. 2025). Distributions of
70 fish are governed by a range of geophysical and biological factors, such as depth, fronts,
71 currents, stratification and salinity, as well as human impacts from fisheries, offshore
72 constructions, dredging, sand extraction and pollution (Nian et al. 2021, Perelman et al. 2023,
73 Gordó-Vilaseca et al. 2024, Rosciszewski-Dodgson & Cirella 2024). Species' responses to

74 environmental variability are often approximated through species distribution models
75 (SDMs), used in ecology and conservation for assessing habitat suitability (Elith and
76 Leathwick, 2009; Guisan et al., 2013). Conceptually rooted in ecological niche theory
77 (Guisan and Zimmermann, 2000), SDMs are statistical techniques aimed at identifying the
78 environmental conditions that species use and rely on for their ecological requirements,
79 which are extrapolated to the surface area of interest (Peterson et al., 2011).

80 Harbour and grey seals are important predators in temperate and subarctic coastal and shelf
81 waters of the North Atlantic (Hall & Russell 2018, Teilmann & Galatius 2018). In the Baltic
82 Sea region, harbour seals range from Skagerrak in the northwest, through Kattegat and the
83 Danish Straits to the southwestern Baltic, with genetically distinct populations in Skagerrak,
84 Kattegat, the southwestern Baltic and around Kalmarsund in the central Baltic Sea (see Fig. 1
85 for place names) (Goodman 1998, Olsen et al. 2014). The grey seal ranges throughout the
86 Baltic area, although to the west; in the southern Baltic Sea, Danish Straits and Kattegat
87 densities are low, as they have only recently started recolonising after local extinctions in the
88 early 20th century (Galatius et al. 2020, Galatius et al. 2024b). All grey seal colonies in the
89 Baltic Sea are connected by geneflow but are genetically distinct from grey seals in the North
90 Sea (McCarthy et al. 2025).

91

92 Grey and harbour seals may compete for space and resources. In areas where prey
93 composition has been analysed, there are considerable dietary overlaps (Wilson & Hammond
94 2015, Scharff-Olsen et al. 2018). In addition, investigations have shown substantial overlap in
95 habitat use (Thompson et al. 1996, Jones et al. 2013), also close to shore (McConnell et al.
96 1999, Dietz et al. 2003, Cordes et al. 2011). In Orkney, Shetland and the Firth of Tay in
97 Scotland, recovery of grey seal populations has coincided with abundance declines of harbour

98 seals, although no direct link has been established (SCOS 2014). Similar dynamics have
99 occurred in the western North Atlantic (Hammill et al. 2010).

100

101 Information on seal distribution in the larger Baltic Sea region is available from monitoring
102 programmes, where seals are counted at their haul-outs during the moulting season and in
103 some areas also during the pupping season (Galatius et al. 2014). This information is limited
104 to haulout distribution and only pertains to these specific periods of the annual cycle. There
105 have been local investigations of seal distribution based on satellite telemetry (e.g. Sjöberg &
106 Ball 2000, Dietz et al. 2013, Oksanen et al. 2014, van Beest et al. 2022), but knowledge
107 regarding pan-Baltic at-sea distribution is lacking. This also prevents comparisons with grey
108 and harbour seal at-sea distribution in the neighboring North Sea region (Carter et al. 2022,
109 Carter et al. 2026).

110

111 Both harbour and grey seals are listed under annexes II and V of the European Union's
112 Habitats Directive, meaning that special areas of conservation must be designated and that
113 exploitation and pressures must be compatible with favourable conservation status.

114 Identifying important habitat for seals is thus important, and increasingly so as anthropogenic
115 pressures are increasing.

116 In the current study, we aim to produce habitat suitability and relative at-sea density maps for
117 grey and harbour seals in the Baltic Sea area using telemetry and census data from the last
118 two decades. Seal distribution is of profound interest in studies of ecosystem processes
119 throughout the area, and in the management of populations in relation to anthropogenic
120 pressures. Additionally, grey seals are currently expanding their range and recolonising the
121 southern and western parts of the area, where harbour seals currently dominate. Hence, we

122 aim to use the resulting models to evaluate the emerging competition between the two species
123 in these areas of increasing overlap.

124

125 **2. Materials and Methods**

126 **2.1 Study area**

127 The study area comprises the Baltic Sea and its adjacent Kattegat and Skagerrak seas (Fig. 1).

128 The Baltic Sea is a semi-enclosed sea in northwestern Europe and the World's largest

129 brackish water basin, stretching 1200 km from 54°N to 66°N, covering temperate and

130 subarctic climate zones. It is connected to the North Atlantic through the narrow and shallow

131 Danish Straits, Kattegat and Skagerrak. There is substantial variation in salinity from 0.1-

132 0.4‰ in the Bothnian Bay through the central Baltic to 2.0-2.5‰ in Kattegat (Leppäranta &

133 Myrberg 2009) and 3.4‰ in Skagerrak (Kristiansen & Aas 2015). The Baltic Sea region is

134 generally shallow, with a mean depth of 54 m and maximum depth of 459 m (Meier et al.

135 2022). Sea surface temperature varies markedly by area and season (Bradtke et al. 2010).

136 These differences in temperature and salinity mean that biodiversity varies greatly, with

137 higher biodiversity in more saline areas (Kniebusch et al. 2019).

138

139 **2.2 Tracking data**

140 We compiled all available telemetry data from harbour seals spanning the area from the

141 Skagerrak to the western Baltic Sea. No data were available from the isolated population in

142 Kalmarsund, and hence, the inner Baltic area was not covered for harbour seals. Grey seal

143 data spanned the entire Baltic Sea region, except Kattegat (Fig. 1). A total of 99 harbour seals

144 (59 males, 38 females, two unknown sex) and 70 grey seals (45 males, 17 females, eight

145 unknown sex) were captured and tagged with GPS or Argos satellite tags at 22 haulout sites

146 across Denmark and Sweden (both species), Norway (harbour seals) and Estonia (grey seals).

147 In Finland only male grey seals were captured in fish traps. All seals were tagged between

148 2000 and 2024 (Tables S1.1 & 1.2 in Supplementary Material S1). A description of capture
149 and handling methods used in each country is provided in Supplementary Material S1.
150 Tracking data collected with GPS tags were cleaned by removing the few outlier locations
151 (n=12 and n=22 for harbour and grey seal data, respectively) that were identified based on
152 unrealistic movements between relocations. Unrealistic movements were defined as
153 relocation events where a seal moved faster than 2.5 m/s between two GPS locations and
154 thereafter returned with the same speed to the first location (van Beest et al. 2019). Argos
155 satellite tags provide less precise position data than GPS tags and these were consequently
156 filtered using the Argos- Filter v7.03 following Dietz et al. (2013). Further processing of
157 tracking data included removal of locations on land, those collected within 24 h after tagging
158 to reduce behavioural bias caused by capture and tagging (van Beest et al. 2018). Following
159 Carter et al. (2022), we removed locations collected during the breeding and moulting
160 seasons (grey seals: February–June, harbour seals: June–August) as behaviour during these
161 seasons is not representative of the key foraging season. After this procedure, we only
162 retained individuals with at least 10 days of tracking data to give all seals meaningful
163 representation, thus removing six harbour and five grey seals. We also removed tracking data
164 of three harbour seals captured in Norway as they spent most of their time in the western
165 Skagerrak (Riaz et al. 2026), outside the boundaries of the area for which environmental data
166 were available (see ‘Environmental data’ below). In the end, we retained data from 90
167 harbour seals and 65 grey seals (Fig. S1.1 and Tables S1.1 & 1.2 in Supplementary Material
168 S1).

169 Given the temporal differences in position interval between GPS and Argos tags, as well as
170 tag programming between countries, the data were interpolated and standardised to a constant
171 4 h time step interval using a continuous-time state space model implemented in the R
172 package ‘aniMotum’ (Jonsen et al. 2023). This procedure is particularly useful when

173 combining GPS and Argos tracking data as it incorporates differences in accuracy level of
174 positional estimates during the standardisation process. When the time difference between
175 two subsequent GPS or Argos locations was >24 hours, the track was split into separate
176 movement bursts prior to standardisation. The final datasets comprised 37,832 at-sea
177 locations for harbour seals (Fig. 2A), and 43,544 at-sea locations for grey seals (Fig. 2B).

178

179 **2.3 Haulout counts**

180 Counts of seals (from Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Germany, Poland, Estonia and Finland;
181 Russian data were not available) on known haul-outs were collected by aerial, boat and drone
182 surveys. Although no grey seals were tagged in Germany and Poland, annual censuses were
183 done during the moulting periods late May to early June for grey seals (Hiby et al. 2007,
184 Galatius et al. 2024a) and August for harbour seals (Härkönen et al. 1999, Galatius et al.
185 2021). Descriptions of the count methods used are provided in Supplementary Material S6.
186 For each seal species and haul-out, count data were averaged across all survey years for
187 further analyses (Fig. 3).

188

189 **2.4 Species distribution modelling**

190 Species distribution models (SDMs) are a broad class of numerical models that aim to predict
191 distribution, density, or habitat suitability of a species across space and time using
192 environmental data (Elith & Leathwick 2009). We followed the analytical approach of Carter
193 et al. (2022) to predict habitat suitability for both seal species separately and weighting the
194 predicted outputs by haulout counts to compute relative at-sea density maps across the study
195 areas.

196

197 *2.4.1 Use-availability study design*

198 SDMs typically contrast environmental conditions at presence or used locations to those
199 encountered at available locations, also known as a “use-availability” study design (Johnson
200 1980, Warton & Aarts 2013). Under this study design, preference for a particular habitat type
201 or environmental condition is inferred where its use is disproportionate to its availability
202 (Aarts et al. 2008, Beyer et al. 2010). In our case, the standardised at-sea seal locations were
203 the used locations. Available locations were randomly drawn from a circular buffer around
204 each used location with the radius set to the maximum distance from a known haul-out by
205 any seal in the cleaned tracking dataset (grey seals: 711 km, harbour seals: 314 km), ensuring
206 that all available locations were potentially accessible to the seals (Matthiopoulos et al.
207 2020). We generated several availability datasets that varied in the ratio of the number of
208 used:available locations (1:1, 1:5, 1:10, 1:15, 1:20, 1:25 and 1:30) to assess at which ratio
209 model estimates stabilised and thus adequately captured the variation in environmental
210 conditions present within the study areas, which is a critical aspect for robust SDM inference
211 (Northrup et al. 2013). The results suggested that model estimates stabilised at a
212 use:availability ratio of 1:10 for harbour seals and 1:20 for grey seals (see Supplementary
213 Material S2 for more details). These ratios were subsequently used in further analyses.

214

215 *2.4.2 Environmental data*

216 Twelve environmental variables were considered as candidate predictor variables in the
217 species-specific SDMs (Table 1; Figs S3.1 & 3.2 in Supplementary Material S3). These
218 variables were selected because of known influence on habitat suitability and movement
219 behaviour of seals or their prey in the Baltic Sea and transition zone to the North Sea
220 (Sjöberg & Ball 2000, Bergström et al. 2013, Dietz et al. 2013, Oksanen et al. 2014, van
221 Beest et al. 2019, van Beest et al. 2022). Static environmental variables included:
222 “bathymetry (m)”, “seabed rugosity (m)” and “sediment type (categorical variable including

223 sand, mud, coarse, and mixed sediments)". Dynamic environmental variables included:
224 "wave exposure (m^2/s)", "current velocity (m/s)", "mixed layer thickness (m)", "sea surface
225 salinity (PSU)", "sea surface height (m)", "sea surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)", "sea bottom
226 oxygen (mmol/m^3)", "sea ice cover (%)", and "distance to known haulout site (km)".
227 Multicollinearity among the 12 candidate predictor variables was substantial with variance
228 inflation factors >20 and Spearman's $\rho > 0.7$ for various variable combinations across the
229 spatial extent of both study areas. To reduce bias and uncertainty due to multicollinearity, we
230 used a stepwise procedure to remove one of two correlated predictor variables and repeated
231 this until all variables had variance inflation factors < 5 and Spearman's $\rho < 0.5$. To decide
232 which of two correlated variables was to be retained, we compared Bayesian Information
233 Criteria (BIC) values of univariate SDMs and retained the variable producing the lowest BIC.
234 We relied on BIC instead of other criteria, e.g. AIC, as BIC imposes a stronger penalty on
235 model complexity and is considered more reliable for identifying the most informative
236 predictor (Aho et al. 2014). Based on this procedure, bathymetry, mixed layer thickness, and
237 ice cover were removed as candidate predictor variables from both the harbour and grey seal
238 SDMs. Sea bottom oxygen and surface salinity were removed as candidate predictor
239 variables for the harbour seal SDM. For the grey seal SDM, we removed sea surface height
240 and sea surface temperature. Ultimately, seven predictor variables remained in each species-
241 specific SDM (Figs S3.1 & 3.2 in Supplementary Material S3).

242

243 For each used and available point in the seal datasets, we georeferenced the XY coordinates
244 with the environmental raster layers and extracted the values of the seven environmental
245 conditions retained as species-specific SDM predictor variables using the R package 'terra'
246 (Hijmans et al., 2024). For the dynamic variables from Copernicus (daily products), we

247 georeferenced the location data and the environmental raster layers by matching them based
248 on both spatial coordinates and the corresponding date of the year.

249

250 2.4.3 Statistical analyses

251 All analyses were conducted using R version 4.5.1 (R Development Core Team 2025).

252 Species-specific SDMs were fitted using generalized additive mixed models (GAMM)

253 through the “bam” function in the R package ‘mgcv’ (Wood 2020). Each SDM was fitted

254 using the equation:

255

$$256 \quad g(P) = \beta_0 + \beta_i + f_1(x_{1k}) + f_2(x_{2k}) + \dots + f_p(x_{pk}) + Y_i + C_k + \epsilon_t \quad (\text{eqn1})$$

257

258 Here, P is the expected outcome of the binomial response variable with used locations coded

259 as 1 and available locations coded as 0 and the error family specified with the logit link

260 function: $g(p) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$. The term β_0 is the global intercept and β_i the fixed effect for the

261 categorical variable sediment type ($i = 1 \dots 4$). The terms $f_1(x_{1k}) + f_2(x_{2k}) + \dots + f_p(x_{pk})$

262 are the continuous covariates fitted as cubic regression splines with shrinkage, meaning that

263 uninformative terms could be penalised to zero, effectively making them linear (Wood,

264 2020). The optimal number of knots (k) of the spline function was determined for each

265 covariate separately by trialling different values ($3 \leq k \leq 8$) and selecting the value for k that

266 minimised the BIC value of the model (Figs S4.1 & 4.2 in Supplementary Material S4). The

267 terms $Y_i + C_j$ are the random effects for the observation’s “year” and “country of tagging”,

268 which were fitted using the “re” basis spline. This was done to indirectly account for the

269 unbalanced data (i.e. differences in tracking duration across individual seals) and to ensure

270 that data-rich years and countries did not have disproportionate influence on overall trends.

271 Finally, ϵ_t has a first-order autoregressive (AR1) correlation structure implemented through

272 the R package ‘itsadug’ (van Rij et al. 2022). The AR1 structure was incorporated to reduce
273 serial autocorrelation in model residuals (ϵ_t) by treating each movement burst (see ‘Tracking
274 data’ above) as a separate time series, i.e. no autocorrelation between movement bursts.
275 Following Carter et al. (2022), we included a weighting function in each SDM, where used
276 points had a value of 1 and available points had a value of 0.1 (1/10) in the harbour seal
277 dataset, while available points had a value of 0.05 (1/20) in the grey seal dataset. Doing so
278 ensured that each set of available points contributed the same weight to the model as the
279 corresponding point that was used.

280

281 Once the final structure of the species-specific SDMs was determined, we evaluated model fit
282 by extracting the amount of deviance explained for the full model as well as for models from
283 which each covariate was dropped one-by-one. We evaluated predictive performance using
284 the k-fold cross-validation procedure as proposed by Wiens et al. (2008) and adapted by
285 Carter et al. (2022) for GAMM models based on use-availability ratios greater than 1:1.
286 Briefly, individual seals were randomly assigned to one of three folds. The GAMM was then
287 fitted to two folds, and predictions were made for the remaining fold (Wiens et al. 2008).
288 Predictive performance of the GAMM was then evaluated by the coefficient of the Spearman
289 rank correlation between binned predicted probabilities and the area-adjusted frequency of
290 presences (Wiens et al. 2008).

291

292 *2.4.4 Habitat suitability maps*

293 The output of the species-specific GAMMs included partial response curves for each
294 environmental variable on the log-odds scale. Habitat suitability raster maps (spatial
295 resolution of 1x1 km) were subsequently generated for each species separately by predicting
296 (on a probability scale) the combined effects of all environmental conditions across the study

297 areas. For the dynamic environmental variables used in the spatial prediction of habitat
298 suitability (Table 1), we averaged the values across the year 2022. For the variable ‘distance
299 to haulout site’, we calculated a raster layer considering all known haul-out locations in the
300 study areas, as opposed to the seal- and haulout site-specific calculations used in the GAMM
301 analyses.

302

303 To incorporate uncertainty into the habitat suitability predictions, we used a Bayesian
304 posterior simulation approach (Marra & Wood 2012, Wood 2020, Carter et al. 2022).
305 Specifically, 100 simulations of the model coefficient vector were drawn from a multivariate
306 normal distribution, with the mean equal to the estimated coefficients and the covariance
307 equal to the unconditional variance-covariance matrix from the fitted GAMMs. For each
308 simulation, we computed the linear predictor by multiplying the model matrix with the
309 simulated coefficients, then applied the inverse logit transformation to obtain predictions on
310 the response scale (Manly et al. 2002). For each raster cell, we then calculated the mean
311 predicted probability and associated 95% credible intervals (i.e. the 2.5th and 97.5th
312 percentiles across simulations).

313

314 To minimize risk of extrapolating model predictions into areas with novel conditions (i.e.
315 environmental values for which the model has no training and testing data, thus making
316 predictions unreliable) a multivariate environmental similarity surfaces (MESS) analysis was
317 performed. Following Elith et al. (2010), we used seal presence locations with associated
318 environmental values as input points and then estimated (dis)similarities with the
319 combination of environmental conditions across the entire study area. The MESS analysis
320 was performed for each seal species separately. Predictions of habitat suitability derived by
321 the GAMMs were subsequently restricted (i.e. masked) to areas where environmental

322 conditions were within the range used by the seals (i.e. MESS similarity value of >0; Fig.
323 S5.1 in Supplementary Material S5). Results of the MESS analyses identified the deeper
324 waters in Skagerrak off the coast of Norway and the colder waters in the northern parts of the
325 Gulf of Bothnia to be dissimilar (i.e. MESS similarity value of <0) from the conditions used
326 by the seals.

327

328 **2.5 Relative population density maps**

329 Spatial predictions of relative at-sea population density were generated per haulout site and
330 species using the corresponding habitat suitability model. Specifically, for each haulout site,
331 raw habitat suitability predictions (on the logit scale) were back-transformed using the
332 inverse logit as in the habitat suitability prediction explained above. Each haul-out-specific
333 prediction surface was then weighted by the mean number of seals counted on each haul-out
334 during all surveys. The weighted, haul-out-specific prediction surfaces were then summed
335 into a cumulative surface layer for the whole study area. The cumulative surface was then
336 normalized by dividing each raster cell value by the total sum of all predicted values and
337 scaled to a percentage, such that the surface sums to 100% (Carter et al. 2022). The unit of the
338 resulting map represents the percentage of the at-sea population estimated to be present in a
339 cell at any one time (% at-sea km⁻²). Cell-wise lower and upper 95% credible intervals of the
340 relative density maps were calculated for each haul-out using the same Bayesian posterior
341 simulation approach as described above for the habitat suitability maps.

342

343 **2.6 Species co-occurrence**

344 To assess inter-specific differences in habitat suitability and relative population density, we
345 calculated Schoener's D niche overlap index (Schoener 1968) and Warren's I niche similarity
346 index (Warren et al. 2008). To do so, we cropped the grey seal prediction surfaces for habitat

347 suitability and relative population density to the same spatial extent as used for the harbour
348 seal analyses (i.e. focus on the southwestern region where both species co-occur). We then
349 calculated the D and I metrics for the mean and associated lower and upper 95% credible
350 interval raster layers, where 0 indicates no overlap or similarity between species and 1
351 indicates complete overlap or similarity in habitat suitability and relative population density.

352

353 **3 Results**

354

355 **3.1 Habitat suitability**

356 The environmental covariates in the species-specific GAMMs explained a total of 54.1% and
357 64.2% of the deviance in habitat suitability for harbour seals and grey seals, respectively
358 (Table S7.1 in Supplementary Material S7). The predictive performance of the GAMMs,
359 estimated using k-fold cross validation, was considered adequate with a mean (SD) r_s of
360 0.897 (0.06) and 0.723 (0.182) for harbour seal and grey seal models, respectively.

361 Predicted mean habitat suitability maps for both species are provided in Fig. 4 (see Figure
362 S7.1 and S7.2 in Supplementary Material S7 for the predicted lower and upper 95% credible
363 interval layers). For both seal species, distance to haul-out was the primary driver of habitat
364 suitability, explaining at 24.6% and 29.2% of the total deviance explained for harbour and
365 grey seals, respectively, with predicted habitat suitability declining with increasing distance
366 from haul-outs (Fig. S7.3 and Table S7.1 in Supplementary Material S7). For harbour seals,
367 sea surface temperature was the second most important predictor of habitat suitability
368 explaining 3.5% of deviation with a preference for mean annual water temperature of <9.75
369 °C, followed by wave exposure explaining 2.5% of the deviance (Fig. S7.3). The remaining
370 variables included in the harbour seal GAMM explained <3% of the total deviation (Table
371 S7.1). For grey seals, sea bottom oxygen was the second most important predictor of habitat

372 suitability explaining 5.9% of deviation with a preference for areas with oxygen levels >300
373 mmol/m³, while increased wave exposure explained 4.7% of the deviance (Fig. S7.3). The
374 remaining variables included in the grey seal GAMM explained <5% of the total deviation
375 (Table S7.1).

376

377 **3.2 Relative population density**

378 The mean relative density maps for both seal species are provided in Fig. 5 (see Fig. S7.4 and
379 S7.5 in Supplementary Material S7 for the predicted lower and upper 95% credible interval
380 layers for harbour seals and grey seals, respectively). The relative density of harbour seals
381 was highest along the west coast of Sweden and the outer Oslo fjord (Fig. 5A). The map also
382 revealed hotspots of harbour seal densities around the islands Hesselø, Anholt and Læsø in
383 Kattegat, and, moreover, that the harbour seal density declined rapidly south of the Danish
384 Straits, towards German waters and the Baltic Sea. The relative density of grey seals was
385 highest within the Archipelago Sea, offshore from the Swedish and Finnish coast (Fig. 5B).
386 Grey seal densities remained high further north into the Bothnian Sea and south towards the
387 Gulf of Riga, while the density declined further east into the Gulf of Finland. The grey seal
388 density also steadily declined towards the Baltic Proper, the southwestern Baltic and into the
389 Kattegat (Fig. 5B).

390

391 **3.3 Species co-occurrence**

392 Focusing on the predicted habitat suitability and relative at-sea population density maps of
393 grey and harbour seals in the southwestern Baltic Sea region (Fig. S7.6 in Supplementary
394 Material S7), we found that the mean proportion of overlap (Schoener's D) exceeded 0.5 for
395 both maps while the mean proportion similarity (Warren's I) exceeded 0.75 for both maps
396 (Fig. 6). Importantly, D and I values were consistently higher when computed from the

397 predicted habitat suitability maps compared to those derived from the relative at-sea density
398 maps (Fig. 6), implying that the densities of both species are not at equilibrium with their
399 suitable habitat.

400

401 **4 Discussion**

402 *Habitat suitability*

403 We present the first comprehensive species distribution models for grey seals and harbour
404 seals in the Baltic Sea region. As central place foragers often return to the same or few
405 specific haul-outs, seal distribution can be expected to be determined by the availability of
406 haul-outs on one hand and distribution of food resources on the other hand (Vance et al.
407 2021). In line with this, both species showed strong habitat preferences related to distance to
408 haul-outs, with harbour seals being more constricted to areas close to haul-outs than grey
409 seals, in agreement with previous studies (e.g. Dietz et al. 2013, Carter et al. 2022, Carter et
410 al. 2026). For harbour seals, suitability was low along the German coast, possibly because
411 many haul-outs have been destroyed by excavation of sand, gravel and rocks (von Nordheim
412 et al. 2011). Suitable at-sea habitats for grey seals were distributed throughout the modelled
413 part of the Baltic Sea area, with the least suitable areas being farther from the coastline. An
414 exception was the southeastern Baltic, bordered by the coasts of Latvia, Lithuania,
415 Kaliningrad and much of the Polish coast, where habitat, also along the coastline, was
416 predicted to have relatively low suitability. One factor behind this may be the availability of
417 only one haul-out locality in the area, at the Vistula River in Poland (Fig. 2B). No grey seals
418 were tagged in this area, but individuals tagged elsewhere used the area (Fig. 2).

419

420 Around the UK, where there is much more variation in sea depth than in our study area,
421 harbour seal habitat preference was inversely related to depth (Carter et al. 2022). We did not

422 find this relationship in our area, which is uniformly shallow, except for deeper waters in
423 northern Skagerrak, which seem to be rarely used by the harbour seals (Fig. 1 and 2A).
424 Harbour seal habitat suitability was also associated with colder surface water temperatures
425 and increased wave exposure. Low surface water temperatures may be associated with
426 upwelling, which may again be associated with prey availability (Lehmann & Myrberg
427 2008). Wave exposure was also important for grey seal distribution and may be a proxy for
428 prey density, being a predictor of distribution for several Baltic fish species (Bergström et al.
429 2013). From the early 20th century, the Baltic Sea has experienced increasing oxygen
430 depletion related to excess eutrophication (Conley et al. 2009, Gustafsson et al. 2012,
431 Carstensen et al. 2014, Meier et al. 2019). As fish will likely avoid areas with low oxygen
432 concentrations (Randall 1970, Stramma et al. 2012, Miethe et al. 2014), it is unsurprising that
433 grey seal habitat suitability is positively related to increased oxygen concentration. Harbour
434 seals may show a similar pattern, but the most severely affected areas in the Baltic are outside
435 of our modelled range for harbour seals, potentially precluding us from detecting a
436 relationship. Also, most of the oxygen-depleted areas in the Baltic are in deeper parts, farther
437 from shore, thus potentially having greater impact on grey seals.

438

439 *Historical context*

440 The harbour and grey seal populations in the Baltic area have experienced drastic abundance
441 fluctuations since the 19th century due to culling, hunting, pollution and virus epidemics
442 (Harding & Härkönen 1999, Härkönen et al. 2006, Härkönen & Isakson 2010, Dietz et al.
443 2021, Carroll et al. 2024, Carroll et al. 2025). As a result, both grey and harbour seals are still
444 recolonising parts of their former range (Galatius et al. 2020, Galatius et al. 2024a, Galatius
445 et al. 2024b). This has implications for our models. In some of the areas of recolonisation,
446 such as the South Funen Archipelago and Little Belt for harbour seals and Kattegat for grey

447 seals, no seals were tagged, and model results in these areas are largely extrapolations of data
448 from areas with seal positions. In these areas, the density models are based on current survey
449 data, which will underestimate seal densities at carrying capacity. Both grey and harbour
450 seals are known to show considerable site fidelity to breeding and haulout sites as well as
451 foraging areas (Pomeroy et al. 2000, Härkönen & Harding 2001, Karlsson et al. 2005, Dietz
452 et al. 2013, Nowak et al. 2025), which will likely result in inertia of expansion to new areas.
453 Comparison of the estimates of actual density with the habitat suitability reveals that for both
454 species, the densities do not thoroughly align as areas with high predicted suitability do not
455 necessarily have high density. For grey seals, densities are greatest in the Stockholm
456 Archipelago and the Finnish Archipelago Sea with lower densities towards the southwestern
457 Baltic, even though the habitat suitability in the latter region is predicted to be equally high.
458 There have already been signs of density dependence in Finland in terms of links between
459 available prey quality and nutritional condition and reproductive rate of the grey seals
460 (Kauhala et al. 2017, Kauhala et al. 2019), so the imbalance between habitat suitability and
461 actual distribution likely reflects inertia in expansion of grey seal distribution.

462

463 *Species overlap and competition*

464 After the local extinction of grey seals in Kattegat and the southern Baltic (Olsen et al. 2018,
465 Galatius et al. 2020), there has been little overlap of the two species in the Baltic Sea region.
466 On one hand this means that the habitat preferences of the species may change during
467 interspecific competition, on the other hand, our models allow some insight into the level of
468 competition. Results of the co-occurrence analyses revealed considerable overlap and
469 similarity in habitat suitability between the two species in the southwestern Baltic Sea and
470 Kattegat. In the southwestern Baltic, there was also similarity regarding density, however, the
471 similarity was clearly higher for habitat suitability. This suggests that despite shared habitat

472 preferences, high-density areas largely remain spatially segregated. Grey seal presence in
473 these areas is growing (Galatius et al. 2020, Galatius et al. 2024b), so suitability and density
474 trend towards higher alignment. This may cause enhanced competition in areas where the
475 habitat is predicted to be suitable for both species, although high predicted suitability may
476 also mean that resources can support co-existence. Around the British Isles, similar models
477 have found high predicted densities for grey seals in areas where harbour seals have suffered
478 rapid, dramatic declines in relation to grey seal recovery (Carter et al. 2022).

479

480 Although our data were collected over 24 years, temporal and spatial gaps prevent us from
481 analysing temporal patterns in the predicted habitat suitability and densities. Harbour seal
482 abundance shows different trends between areas in the Baltic region. In the southwestern
483 Baltic Sea, the harbour seal population is growing, despite increasing numbers of grey seals
484 (Galatius et al. 2021, HELCOM 2023, Carroll et al. 2025). Here, harbour seals were driven to
485 the brink of extinction in the 1970s (Søndergaard et al. 1976, Härkönen & Isakson 2010),
486 which may explain why this population is still below the carrying capacity of the
487 environment and growing despite increased presence of grey seals. In Kattegat and
488 Skagerrak, where there are still few grey seals (Galatius et al. 2024b), harbour seal abundance
489 has been declining over the last decade, probably because of competition with fisheries and
490 habitat degradation (Carroll et al. 2025).

491

492 The potential for future interspecific competition indicated by our models is supported by
493 observations of declining harbour seal abundance following grey seal recovery in other areas
494 (Thompson et al. 2019), overlaps in diet (Wilson & Hammond 2015, Scharff-Olsen et al.
495 2018), and sources indicating that grey seals were previously more abundant than harbour
496 seals in the southwestern Baltic and Kattegat (Søndergaard et al. 1976, Olsen et al. 2018).

497 Besides competition for resources, it has also been documented that grey seals may kill
498 harbour seals in the Baltic region (Westphal et al. 2023).

499

500 *Caveats*

501 Along with suitable haulout sites, prey density is known to be important in determining seal
502 habitat suitability (Thompson et al. 1996, McConnell et al. 1999, Vance et al. 2021). Our
503 models do not directly include prey density, but rather proxies. The models presented here are
504 built on more than 20 years of telemetry data from this dynamic environment. There have
505 been drastic changes in the Baltic Sea ecosystem during this period, including climate
506 change, oxygen depletion and fisheries activities which affect the abundance, distribution and
507 composition of fish, as well as activities causing disturbance of seals, such as commercial and
508 leisure activities and seal hunting (Carstensen et al. 2014, Hansson et al. 2018, Meier et al.
509 2022, Cerwenka et al. 2023, Svedäng 2023, Moll et al. 2024, van Meurs et al. 2024,
510 Lundström et al. 2025). With data of higher temporal resolution, future models could
511 investigate the effects of changes in anthropogenic pressures on habitat suitability and
512 densities.

513 Comprehensive coverage of an area at the scale of the Baltic Sea is challenging, and although
514 the seals moved throughout most of the Baltic Sea, tagging sites were unequally distributed
515 with western Estonian waters and the southwestern Swedish and Danish Baltic more
516 comprehensively covered than other areas for grey seals (Fig 2B). For harbour seals, there
517 were no data available from seals tagged along the Swedish coasts of Skagerrak and Kattegat,
518 although more than 40% of the seals in the area are counted here during the moulting season
519 (ICES 2024). Due to low densities, grey seals were not tagged in Kattegat. The indication
520 from the analyses is that the effects of this unequal distribution on the validity of the models
521 are minor; the predictive performance (k-fold) of the models was high, indicating that the

522 models worked well throughout the heterogeneous habitat of the study area. Age and sex
523 were not considered in the models, as separate models for different segments of the
524 populations would reduce the amount of data and their spatial coverage, causing loss of
525 predictive power. There are known differences in movement behaviour between sexes and
526 age-classes of seals with juveniles typically having larger ranges (Lowry et al. 2001, Dietz et
527 al. 2013). For harbour seals, there was a higher proportion of adults tagged in Norway than in
528 Sweden and Denmark and for grey seals, all seals tagged in Finland were males while only a
529 couple of the seals tagged in Denmark were adults (Supplementary Table S1). The effects of
530 such differences are partially mitigated by excluding data from the breeding and moulting
531 seasons but could be a focus for future efforts on seal habitat suitability in the region.
532 The haulout counts used to calculate relative densities at sea represent seal distribution during
533 the annual moulting seasons. This is the only season during which seals are counted
534 throughout the study area and distribution is known to be different during the breeding season
535 (Galatius et al. 2020, Galatius et al. 2024a). Further differences in are likely to be present
536 outside the breeding and moulting seasons, particularly for grey seals, which move over
537 wider areas than harbour seals and potentially use different areas in different seasons (Russell
538 et al. 2013).

539

540 *Conclusions*

541 We present the most comprehensive analysis of at-sea habitat suitability and density of two
542 apex predators in the Baltic Sea region. As such, the outputs may serve as valuable tools for
543 managers and ecologists assessing threats, pressures and interactions of these species with the
544 ecosystem at large. Our analyses provide evidence that current distributions of both species
545 are not at equilibrium with the available suitable habitat. This reflects the dramatic history of
546 seals in the region over the past centuries, with hunting, culling, pollution, haul-out

547 destruction and virus epidemics causing massive fluctuations in abundances and ranges, from
548 which the populations are still recovering. Our study also indicates a substantial overlap in
549 habitat suitability between the two species in the southwestern Baltic and Kattegat. In these
550 areas, harbour seals are currently more abundant than grey seals. Harbour seals are already in
551 decline in Kattegat and Skagerrak, although grey seals only occur in low numbers. As the
552 habitat suitability and distribution of both species is likely to change with interspecific
553 competition, predation and environmental changes, we encourage continued tagging efforts
554 and monitoring of haul-outs to understand how the changing environment affects the habitat
555 use of the two largest marine predators in the Baltic Sea region.

556 **Acknowledgements**

557 We thank Debbie J. F. Russell and Matt I. D. Carter for sharing their code to implement the k-
558 fold cross-validation of GAMMs. We thank K. T. Nilssen, M. Biuw, E. Moland, M.
559 Poltermann and M. Kristiansen for their contribution to the Norwegian data collection and
560 curation. We also like to thank a long list of assistants and volunteers helping out in the field
561 during seal tagging and surveys through the years.

562 **Funding information**

563 Funding for this study was provided by the GES4SEAS and OBAMA-NEXT projects funded
564 under the Horizon Europe program (grant agreements 101059877 and 101091642). CF was
565 supported by the Horizon Europe project MARHAB (grant agreement 101135307). We are
566 grateful to the funding sources and colleagues contributing to the multitude of tagging studies
567 providing data for this study (see referred studies for details). Add surveys in all the countries
568 like NOVANA, Danish Ministry of Environment.

569 **Conflict of interest statement**

570 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

571 **Data availability statement**

572 The datasets generated in this study will be made freely available at zenodo.org on
573 publication.

574 **Author contributions**

575 Anders Galatius and Floris M. van Beest conceived the study, curated and managed data and
576 drafted the manuscript. Floris van Beest conducted analyses. Anders Galatius, Floris van
577 Beest, Jacob Carstensen and Jonas Teilmann interpreted the results. Anders Galatius, Jonas
578 Teilmann, Markus Ahola, Anja Carlsson, Rune Dietz, Carla Freitas, Inari Helle, Ivar Jüssi,
579 Mart Jüssi, Mervi Kunnasranta and Morten Tange Olsen collected the data. All authors
580 contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

581

582 **References**

583

584 Aho K, Derryberry D, Peterson T (2014) Model selection for ecologists: the worldviews of
585 AIC and BIC. *Ecology* 95:631-636

586 Bennington S, Rayment W, Dawson S (2020) Putting prey into the picture: improvements
587 to species distribution models for bottlenose dolphins in Doubtful Sound, New
588 Zealand. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 653:191-204

589 Benoit-Bird KJ, Battaile BC, Heppell SA, Hoover B, Irons D, Jones N, Kuletz KJ, Nordstrom
590 CA, Paredes R, Suryan RM, Waluk CM, Trites AW (2013) Prey patch patterns
591 predict habitat use by top marine predators with diverse foraging strategies. *Plos*
592 *One* 8

593 Bergström U, Sundblad G, Downie AL, Snickars M, Boström C, Lindegarth M (2013)
594 Evaluating eutrophication management scenarios in the Baltic Sea using species
595 distribution modelling. *J Appl Ecol* 50:680-690

596 Beyer HL, Haydon DT, Morales JM, Frair JL, Hebblewhite M, Mitchell M, Matthiopoulos J
597 (2010) The interpretation of habitat preference metrics under use-availability
598 designs. *Philos T R Soc B* 365:2245-2254

599 Bradtke K, Herman A, Urbanski JA (2010) Spatial and interannual variations of seasonal
600 sea surface temperature patterns in the Baltic Sea. *Oceanologia* 52:345-362

601 Carroll D, Ahola MP, Carlsson AM, Galatius A, Nilssen KT, Härkönen T, Harding KC (2025)
602 Declining harbour seal abundance in a previously recovering meta-population.
603 *Plos One* 20:e0326933

604 Carroll D, Ahola MP, Carlsson AM, Sköld M, Harding KC (2024) 120-years of ecological
605 monitoring data shows that the risk of overhunting is increased by environmental
606 degradation for an isolated marine mammal population: The Baltic grey seal. *J*
607 *Anim Ecol* 93:525-539

608 Carstensen J, Andersen JH, Gustafsson BG, Conley DJ (2014) Deoxygenation of the
609 Baltic Sea during the last century. *P Natl Acad Sci USA* 111:5628-5633

610 Carter MID, Boehme L, Cronin MA, Duck CD, Grecian WJ, Hastie GD, Jessopp M,
611 Matthiopoulos J, McConnell BJ, Miller DL, Morris CD, Moss SEW, Thompson D,
612 Thompson PM, Russell DJF (2022) Sympatric seals, satellite tracking and
613 protected areas: habitat-based distribution estimates for conservation and
614 management. *Front Mar Sci* 9

615 Carter MID, Aarts G, van Beest FM, Bivins M, Brasseur SMJM, Dietz R, Duck CD, Galatius
616 A, Gilles A, Haelters J, Hastie GD, Jessopp M, Morris CD, Moss SEW, Nabe-
617 Nielsen J, Nachtsheim DA, Schaffeld T, Schop J, Siebert U, Teilmann J, Thompson
618 D, Thompson PM, Vincent C, Russell DJF (2026) At-sea distribution of seals on
619 the Northwest European Shelf: Towards transboundary conservation and
620 management. *J Appl Ecol* 63

621 Cerwenka AF, Brandner J, Dashinov D, Geist J (2023) Small but mighty: the round goby
622 (*Neogobius melanostomus*) as a model species of biological invasions.
623 *Diversity-Basel* 15:e528

624 Conley DJ, Björck S, Bonsdorff E, Carstensen J, Destouni G, Gustafsson BG, Hietanen S,
625 Kortekaas M, Kuosa H, Meier HEM, Müller-Karulis B, Nordberg K, Norkko A,
626 Nürnberg G, Pitkänen H, Rabalais NN, Rosenberg R, Savchuk OP, Slomp CP, Voss
627 M, Wulff F, Zillén L (2009) Hypoxia-related processes in the Baltic Sea. *Environ*
628 *Sci Technol* 43:3412-3420

629 Cordes LS, Duck CD, Mackey BL, Hall AJ, Thompson PM (2011) Long-term patterns in
630 harbour seal site-use and the consequences for managing protected areas.
631 Anim Conserv 14:430-438

632 Dietz R, Sonne C, Jenssen BM, Das K, de Wit CA, Harding KC, Siebert U, Olsen MT (2021)
633 The Baltic Sea: an ecosystem with multiple stressors. Environ Int 147:e106324

634 Dietz R, Teilmann J, Andersen SM, Rigét F, Olsen MT (2013) Movements and site fidelity
635 of harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*) in Kattegat, Denmark, with implications for the
636 epidemiology of the phocine distemper virus. ICES Journal of Marine Science
637 70:186-195

638 Dietz R, Teilmann J, Henriksen OD, Laidre K (2003) Movements of seals from Rødsand
639 seal sanctuary monitored by satellite telemetry. Relative importance of the
640 Nysted Offshore Wind Farm area to the seals. National Environmental Research
641 Institute Technical Report, Book 429, Roskilde, Denmark

642 Duarte CM, Chapuis L, Collin SP, Costa DP, Devassy RP, Eguiluz VM, Erbe C, Gordon
643 TAC, Halpern BS, Harding HR, Havlik MN, Meekan M, Merchant ND, Miksis-Olds
644 JL, Parsons M, Predragovic M, Radford AN, Radford CA, Simpson SD,
645 Slabbekoorn H, Staaterman E, Van Opzeeland IC, Winderen J, Zhang XL, Juanes F
646 (2021) The soundscape of the Anthropocene ocean. Science 371:583

647 Elith J, Kearney M, Phillips S (2010) The art of modelling range-shifting species. Methods
648 Ecol Evol 1:330-342

649 Elith J, Leathwick JR (2009) Species distribution models: ecological explanation and
650 prediction across space and time. Annu Rev Ecol Evol S 40:677-697

651 Galatius A, Ahola M, Härkönen T, Jüssi I, Jüssi M, Karlsson O, Verevkin M (2014)
652 Guidelines for seal abundance monitoring in the HELCOM area 2014. HELCOM
653 <http://www.helcom.fi/Documents/Action%20areas/Monitoring%20and%20assessment/Manuals%20and%20Guidelines/Guidelines%20for%20Seal%20Abundance%20Monitoring%20HELCOM%202014.pdf>
654
655

656 Galatius A, Dietz R, Olsen MT, Teilmann J (2024a) Recolonisation of former habitat by
657 harbour seals in southern Denmark despite intense anthropogenic activity. J Mar
658 Biol Assoc Uk 104

659 Galatius A, Engbo SG, Teilmann J, van Beest FM (2021) Using environmental variation to
660 optimize aerial surveys of harbour seals. ICES Journal of Marine Science
661 78:1500-1507

662 Galatius A, Olsen MT, Allentoft-Larsen M, Balle JD, Kyhn LA, Sveegaard S, Teilmann J
663 (2024b) Evidence of distribution overlap between Atlantic and Baltic grey seals. J
664 Mar Biol Assoc Uk 104

665 Galatius A, Teilmann J, Dähne M, Ahola M, Westphal L, Kyhn LA, Pawliczka I, Olsen MT,
666 Dietz R (2020) Grey seal *Halichoerus grypus* recolonisation of the southern Baltic
667 Sea, Danish Straits and Kattegat. Wildlife Biology
668 2020:<https://doi.org/10.2981/wlb.00711>

669 Goodman SJ (1998) Patterns of extensive genetic differentiation and variation among
670 European harbor seals (*Phoca vitulina*) revealed using microsatellite DNA
671 polymorphisms. Mol Biol Evol 15:104-118

672 Gordó-Vilaseca C, Costello MJ, Coll M, Jüterbock A, Reiss H, Stephenson F (2024)
673 Future trends of marine fish biomass distributions from the North Sea to the
674 Barents Sea. Nat Commun 15:e5637

675 Gustafsson BG, Schenk F, Blenckner T, Eilola K, Meier HEM, Müller-Karulis B, Neumann
676 T, Ruoho-Airola T, Savchuk OP, Zorita E (2012) Reconstructing the development
677 of Baltic Sea eutrophication 1850-2006. *Ambio* 41:534-548

678 Hall AJ, Russell DJF (2018) Gray seal *Halichoerus grypus*. In: Würsig B, Thewissen JGM,
679 Kovacs K (eds) *Encyclopedia of Marine Mammals*. Academic Press, San Diego

680 Hammill MO, Bowen WD, Sjare B (2010) Status of harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*) in
681 Atlantic Canada. *NAMMCO Scientific Publications* 8:175-190

682 Hansson S, Bergström U, Bonsdorff E, Härkönen T, Jepsen N, Kautsky L, Lundström K,
683 Lunneryd S-G, Ovegård M, Salmi J, Sendek D, Vetemaa M (2018) Competition for
684 the fish – fish extraction from the Baltic Sea by humans, aquatic mammals, and
685 birds. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 75:999-1008

686 Harding KC, Härkönen TJ (1999) Development in the Baltic grey seal (*Halichoerus*
687 *grypus*) and ringed seal (*Pusa hispida*) populations during the 20th century.
688 *Ambio* 28:619-627

689 Hazen EL, Abrahms B, Brodie S, Carroll G, Jacox MG, Savoca MS, Scales KL, Sydeman
690 WJ, Bograd SJ (2019) Marine top predators as climate and ecosystem sentinels.
691 *Front Ecol Environ* 17:565-573

692 Heide-Jørgensen MP, Härkönen TJ (1988) Rebuilding seal stocks in the Kattegat-
693 Skagerrak. *Mar Mammal Sci* 4:231-246

694 HELCOM (2009) Eutrophication in the Baltic Sea. An integrated thematic assessment of
695 the effects of nutrient enrichment in the Baltic Sea region. *Baltic Sea*
696 *Environment Proceedings*, Book 115B, Helsinki

697 HELCOM (2023) Population trends and abundance of seals. HELCOM core indicator
698 report. Online. [https://indicators.helcom.fi/wp-](https://indicators.helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Population-trends-and-abundance-of-seals-Harbour-seals_Final_April_2023-1.pdf)
699 [content/uploads/2023/04/Population-trends-and-abundance-of-seals-Harbour-](https://indicators.helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Population-trends-and-abundance-of-seals-Harbour-seals_Final_April_2023-1.pdf)
700 [seals_Final_April_2023-1.pdf](https://indicators.helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Population-trends-and-abundance-of-seals-Harbour-seals_Final_April_2023-1.pdf)

701 Hiby L, Lundberg T, Karlsson O, Watkins J, Jüssi M, Jüssi I, Helander B (2007) Estimates
702 of the size of the Baltic grey seal population based on photo-identification data.
703 *NAMMCO Scientific Publications* 6:163-175

704 Härkönen T, Dietz R, Reijnders P, Teilmann J, Harding K, Hall A, Brasseur S, Siebert U,
705 Goodman SJ, Jepsen PD, Rasmussen TD, Thompson P (2006) The 1988 and 2002
706 phocine distemper virus epidemics in European harbour seals. *Dis Aquat Organ*
707 68:115-130

708 Härkönen T, Harding KC (2001) Spatial structure of harbour seal populations and the
709 implications thereof. *Can J Zool* 79:2115-2127

710 Härkönen T, Harding KC, Lunneryd SG (1999) Age- and sex-specific behaviour in harbour
711 seals (*Phoca vitulina*) leads to biased estimates of vital population parameters. *J*
712 *Appl Ecol* 36:825-841

713 Härkönen T, Isakson E (2010) Status of harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*) in the Baltic
714 proper. *NAMMCO Scientific Publications* 8:71-76

715 ICES (2024) Working Group on Marine Mammal Ecology. *ICES Scientific Reports*, Book
716 6:82

717 Jackson JBC, Kirby MX, Berger WH, Bjorndal KA, Botsford LW, Bourque BJ, Bradbury RH,
718 Cooke R, Erlandson J, Estes JA, Hughes TP, Kidwell S, Lange CB, Lenihan HS,
719 Pandolfi JM, Peterson CH, Steneck RS, Tegner MJ, Warner RR (2001) Historical
720 overfishing and the recent collapse of coastal ecosystems. *Science* 293:629-638

721 Johnson DH (1980) The comparison of usage and availability measurements for
722 evaluating resource preference. *Ecology* 61:65-71

723 Jones E, McConnell BJ, Sparling C, Matthiopoulos J (2013) Grey and harbour seal usage
724 maps. Marine Mammal Scientific Support Research Programme
725 <http://www.gov.scot/Resource/0043/00437053.pdf>

726 Jonsen ID, Grecian WJ, Phillips L, Carroll G, McMahon C, Harcourt RG, Hindell MA,
727 Patterson TA (2023) aniMotum, an R package for animal movement data: Rapid
728 quality control, behavioural estimation and simulation. *Methods Ecol Evol*
729 14:806-816

730 Kappa F, Härkönen T, Freitas C, Carroll D, Harding KC (2025) Shifting harbor seal (*Phoca*
731 *vitulina*) diet may reflect ecosystem changes in Skagerrak. *Mar Mammal Sci*
732 42:e70069

733 Karlsson O, Hiby L, Lundberg T, Jüssi M, Jüssi I, Helander B (2005) Photo-identification,
734 site fidelity, and movement of female gray seals (*Halichoerus grypus*) between
735 haul-outs in the Baltic Sea. *Ambio* 34:628-634

736 Kauhala K, Bäcklin BM, Raitaniemi J, Harding KC (2017) The effect of prey quality and ice
737 conditions on the nutritional status of Baltic gray seals of different age groups.
738 *Mammal Res* 62:351-362

739 Kauhala K, Korpinen S, Lehtiniemi M, Raitaniemi J (2019) Reproductive rate of a top
740 predator, the grey seal, as an indicator of the changes in the Baltic food web.
741 *Ecol Indic* 102:693-703

742 Kniebusch M, Meiert HEM, Radtke H (2019) Changing salinity gradients in the Baltic Sea
743 as a consequence of altered freshwater budgets. *Geophys Res Lett* 46:9739-
744 9747

745 Kokko H, Helle E, Lindström J, Ranta E, Sipilä T, Courchamp F (1999) Backcasting
746 population sizes of ringed and grey seals in the Baltic and Lake Saimaa during
747 the 20th century. *Ann Zool Fenn* 36:65-73

748 Kristiansen T, Aas E (2015) Water type quantification in the Skagerrak, the Kattegat and
749 off the Jutland west coast. *Oceanologia* 57:177-195

750 Lehmann A, Myrberg K (2008) Upwelling in the Baltic Sea - a review. *J Marine Syst* 74:S3-
751 S12

752 Leppäranta M, Myrberg K (2009) Physical oceanography of the Baltic Sea. Springer-
753 Verlag, Berlin, Germany

754 Lowry LF, Frost KJ, Ver Hoef JM, DeLong RA (2001) Movements of satellite-tagged
755 subadult and adult harbor seals in Prince William Sound, Alaska. *Mar Mammal*
756 *Sci* 17:835-861

757 Lundström K, Carlsson AM, Karlsson M, Mion M, Eriksson P, Ahola MP (2025) The
758 reintroduction grey seal hunting in Sweden – A review of hunting and seal
759 population data (2001-2024). *NAMMCO Scientific Publications* 14:3.8086

760 Manly BFJ, McDonald LL, Thomas DL, McDonald TL, Erickson WP (2002) Resource
761 selection by animals: statistical analysis and design for field studies. Kluwer
762 Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands

763 Marra G, Wood SN (2012) Coverage properties of confidence intervals for generalized
764 additive model components. *Scand J Stat* 39:53-74

765 Matthiopoulos J, Fieberg J, Aarts G, Barraquand F, Kendall BE (2020) Within reach?
766 Habitat availability as a function of individual mobility and spatial structuring.
767 *Am Nat* 195:1009-1026

768 Maúre ED, Terauchi G, Ishizaka J, Clinton N, DeWitt M (2021) Globally consistent
769 assessment of coastal eutrophication. *Nat Commun* 12:e6142

770 McCarthy ML, Cammen KM, Granquist SM, Dietz R, Teilmann J, Thostesen CB,
771 Kjeldgaard S, Valtonen M, Kunnasranta M, Jenssen BM, Ahola MP, Bäcklin BM,
772 Bowen WD, Puryear WB, Runstadler JA, Russell DJF, Galatius A, Olsen MT (2025)
773 Range-wide genomic analysis reveals regional and meta-population dynamics of
774 decline and recovery in the grey seal. *Mol Ecol* 34:e17824

775 McConnell BJ, Fedak MA, Lovell P, Hammond PS (1999) Movements and foraging areas
776 of grey seals in the North Sea. *J Appl Ecol* 36:573-590

777 Meier HEM, Eilola K, Almroth-Rosell E, Schimanke S, Kniebusch M, Höglund A,
778 Pemberton P, Liu Y, Väli G, Saraiva S (2019) Disentangling the impact of nutrient
779 load and climate changes on Baltic Sea hypoxia and eutrophication since 1850
780 (vol 53, pg 1145, 2019). *Clim Dynam* 53:1167-1169

781 Meier HEM, Kniebusch M, Dieterich C, Gröger M, Zorita E, Elmgren R, Myrberg K, Ahola
782 MP, Bartosova A, Bonsdorff E, Börgel F, Capell R, Carlén I, Carlund T, Carstensen
783 J, Christensen OB, Dierschke V, Frauen C, Frederiksen M, Gaget E, Galatius A,
784 Haapala JJ, Halkka A, Hugelius G, Hünicke B, Jaagus J, Jüssi M, Käyhkö J, Kirchner
785 N, Kjellström E, Kulinski K, Lehmann A, Lindström G, May W, Miller PA, Mohrholz
786 V, Müller-Karulis B, Pavón-Jordán D, Quante M, Reckermann M, Rutgersson A,
787 Savchuk OP, Stendel M, Tuomi L, Viitasalo M, Weisse R, Zhang WY (2022) Climate
788 change in the Baltic Sea region: a summary. *Earth Syst Dynam* 13:457-593

789 Miethe T, Gröhsler T, Böttcher U, von Dorrien C (2014) The effects of periodic marine
790 inflow into the Baltic Sea on the migration patterns of Western Baltic spring-
791 spawning herring. *Ices Journal of Marine Science* 71:519-527

792 Moll D, Asmus H, Blöcker A, Böttcher U, Conradt J, Färber L, Funk N, Funk S, Gutte H,
793 Hinrichsen HH, Kotterba P, Krumme U, Madiraca F, Meier HEM, Meyer S, Moritz T,
794 Otto SA, Pinto G, Polte P, Riekhof MC, Sarrazin V, Scotti M, Voss R, Winkler H,
795 Möllmann C (2024) A climate vulnerability assessment of the fish community in
796 the Western Baltic Sea. *Sci Rep-Uk* 14:e16184

797 Moore SE (2008) Marine mammals as ecosystem sentinels. *J Mammal* 89:534-540

798 Nian R, Yuan Q, He H, Geng X, Su CW, He B, Lendasse A (2021) The identification and
799 prediction in abundance variation of Atlantic cod *via* long short-term memory
800 with periodicity, time-frequency co-movement, and lead-lag effect across sea
801 surface temperature, sea surface salinity, catches, and prey biomass from 1919
802 to 2016. *Front Mar Sci* 8:e665716

803 Northrup JM, Hooten MB, Anderson CR, Wittemyer G (2013) Practical guidance on
804 characterizing availability in resource selection functions under a use-availability
805 design. *Ecology* 94:1456-1463

806 Nowak BVR, Bowen WD, Lidgard DC, Den Heyer CE (2025) Habitat fidelity of adult grey
807 seals over multiple years in a changing marine ecosystem. *Mov Ecol* 13:e82

808 Oksanen SM, Ahola MP, Lehtonen E, Kunnasranta M (2014) Using movement data of
809 Baltic grey seals to examine foraging-site fidelity: implications for seal-fishery
810 conflict mitigation. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 507:297-308

811 Olsen MT, Andersen LW, Dietz R, Teilmann J, Härkönen T, Siegismund HR (2014)
812 Integrating genetic data and population viability analyses for the identification of
813 harbour seal (*Phoca vitulina*) populations and management units. *Mol Ecol*
814 23:815-831

815 Olsen MT, Galatius A, Härkönen T (2018) The history and effects of seal-fishery conflicts
816 in Denmark Marine Ecology Progress Series 595

817 Perelman JN, Lacroix Y, Escobar-Flores P, Firing E, Drazen JC (2023) Eddies and fronts
818 influence pelagic communities across the eastern Pacific ocean. Prog Oceanogr
819 211:e102967

820 Pomeroy PP, Twiss SD, Redman P (2000) Philopatry, site fidelity and local kin
821 associations within grey seal breeding colonies. Ethology 106:899-919

822 R Development Core Team (2025) R: A language and environment for statistical
823 computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria

824 Randall DJ (1970) Gas exchange in fish. In: Hoar WS, Randall DJ (eds) Fish Physiology,
825 Book Volume 4: The nervous system, Circulation, and Respiration. Academic
826 Press, San Diego, CA

827 Reusch TBH, Dierking J, Andersson HC, Bonsdorff E, Carstensen J, Casini M, Czajkowski
828 M, Hasler B, Hinsby K, Hyytiäinen K, Johannesson K, Jomaa S, Jormalainen V,
829 Kuosa H, Kurland S, Laikre L, MacKenzie BR, Margonski P, Melzner F, Oesterwind
830 D, Ojaveer H, Refsgaard JC, Sandström A, Schwarz G, Tonderski K, Winder M,
831 Zandersen M (2018) The Baltic Sea as a time machine for the future coastal
832 ocean. Sci Adv 4:e8195

833 Riaz J, Nilssen KT, Biuw M, Moland E, Poltermann M, Kristiansen M, Freitas C (2026)
834 Haul-out site use and connectivity of harbour seals between management units
835 in southern Scandinavia. Ecol Evol 16:e72718

836 Rosciszewski-Dodgson MJ, Cirella GT (2024) Environmental drivers affecting the status
837 of top commercial fish stocks in the Baltic Sea: review. Front Mar Sci
838 11:e1399707

839 Russell DJF, McConnell B, Thompson D, Duck C, Morris C, Harwood J, Matthiopoulos J
840 (2013) Uncovering the links between foraging and breeding regions in a highly
841 mobile mammal. J Appl Ecol 50:499-509

842 Scharff-Olsen CH, Galatius A, Teilmann J, Dietz R, Andersen SM, Jarnit S, Kroner A-M,
843 Botnen AB, Lundström K, Møller PR, Olsen MT (2018) Diet of seals in the Baltic
844 Sea region: a synthesis of published and new data from 1968 to 2013. Ices J Mar
845 Sci 76:284-297

846 Schoener TW (1968) Anolis lizards of Bimini - resource partitioning in a complex fauna.
847 Ecology 49:704-726

848 SCOS (2014) Scientific advice on matters related to the management of seal
849 populations: 2014. University of St Andrews, St Andrews, UK
850 <http://www.smru.st-and.ac.uk/documents/2259.pdf>

851 Sjöberg M, Ball JP (2000) Grey seal, *Halichoerus grypus*, habitat selection around
852 haulout sites in the Baltic Sea: bathymetry or central-place foraging? Can J Zool
853 78:1661-1667

854 Sonne C, Siebert U, Gonnens K, Desforges JP, Eulaers I, Persson S, Roos A, Bäcklin BM,
855 Kauhala K, Olsen MT, Harding KC, Treu G, Galatius A, Andersen-Ranberg E, Gross
856 S, Lakemeyer J, Lehnert K, Lam SS, Peng WX, Dietz R (2020) Health effects from
857 contaminant exposure in Baltic Sea birds and marine mammals: a review.
858 Environ Int 139:e105725

859 Stramma L, Prince ED, Schmidtko S, Luo JG, Hoolihan JP, Visbeck M, Wallace DWR,
860 Brandt P, Körtzinger A (2012) Expansion of oxygen minimum zones may reduce
861 available habitat for tropical pelagic fishes. Nat Clim Change 2:33-37

862 Svedäng H (2023) The Development of Fish Stocks and Fisheries in the Baltic Sea Since
863 the Last Glaciation. Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Climate Science. Oxford
864 Research Encyclopedias, Oxford, UK

865 Søndergaard NO, Joensen AH, Hansen EB (1976) Sælernes forekomst og sæljagten i
866 Danmark. Dansk Vildtundersøgelser 26:1-80

867 Teilmann J, Galatius A (2018) Harbor seal *Phoca vitulina*. In: Würsig B, Thewissen JGM,
868 Kovacs K (eds) Encyclopedia of Marine Mammals 3rd Edition. Elsevier, San Diego

869 Thompson D, Duck CD, Morris CD, Russell DJF (2019) The status of harbour seals
870 (*Phoca vitulina*) in the UK. Aquat Conserv 29:40-60

871 Thompson PM, McConnell BJ, Tollit DJ, Mackay A, Hunter C, Racey PA (1996)
872 Comparative distribution, movements and diet of harbour and grey seals from
873 the Moray Firth, NE Scotland. J Appl Ecol 33:1572-1584

874 van Beest FM, Dietz R, Galatius A, Kyhn LA, Sveegaard S, Teilmann J (2022) Forecasting
875 shifts in habitat suitability of three marine predators suggests a rapid decline in
876 inter-specific overlap under future climate change. Ecol Evol 12: e9083

877 van Beest FM, Mews S, Elkenkamp S, Schuhmann P, Tsolak D, Wobbe T, Bartolino V,
878 Bastardie F, Dietz R, von Dorrien C, Galatius A, Karlsson O, McConnell B, Nabe-
879 Nielsen J, Olsen MT, Teilmann J, Langrock R (2019) Classifying grey seal
880 behaviour in relation to environmental variability and commercial fishing activity
881 - a multivariate hidden Markov model. Sci Rep-Uk 9

882 van Beest FM, Teilmann J, Hermannsen L, Galatius A, Mikkelsen L, Sveegaard S, Balle
883 JD, Dietz R, Nabe-Nielsen J (2018) Fine-scale movement responses of free-
884 ranging harbour porpoises to capture, tagging and short-term noise pulses from
885 a single airgun. Roy Soc Open Sci 5

886 van Meurs E, Moland E, Bjørge A, Freitas C (2024) Haulout patterns of harbour seal
887 colonies in the Norwegian Skagerrak, as monitored through time-lapse camera
888 surveys. Diversity-Basel 16:e38

889 van Rij J, Wieling M, Baayen RH, van Rijn D (2022) itsadug: Interpreting Time Series and
890 Autocorrelated Data Using GAMMs [WWW Document]. [https://cran.r-](https://cran.r-project.org/package=itsadug)
891 [project.org/package=itsadug](https://cran.r-project.org/package=itsadug) (accessed 3.28.25)

892 Vance HM, Hooker SK, Mikkelsen L, van Neer A, Teilmann J, Siebert U, Johnson M (2021)
893 Drivers and constraints on offshore foraging in harbour seals. Sci Rep-Uk
894 11:e6514

895 von Nordheim H, Maschner K, Liebschner A (2011) Die Rückkehr der Kegelrobben an die
896 deutsche Ostseeküste. Meer & Museum 23:237-250

897 Warren DL, Glor RE, Turelli M (2008) Environmental niche equivalency versus
898 conservatism: quantitative approaches to niche evolution. Evolution 62:2868-
899 2883

900 Warton D, Aarts G (2013) Advancing our thinking in presence-only and used-available
901 analysis. J Anim Ecol 82:1125-1134

902 Westphal L, Klemens L, Reif F, van Neer A, Dähne M (2023) First evidence of grey seal
903 predation on marine mammals in the German Baltic Sea. J Sea Res 192:e102350

904 Wiens TS, Dale BC, Boyce MS, Kershaw GP (2008) Three way *k*-fold cross-validation of
905 resource selection functions. Ecol Model 212:244-255

906 Wilson L, Hammond P (2015) Comparing the diet of harbour and grey seals in Scotland
907 and eastern England. Sea Mammal Research Unit Report to Scottish
908 Government. University of St Andrews, St. Andrews, UK

909 <https://data.marine.gov.scot/sites/default/files/SMFS%20Vol%207%20No%2019>
910 [.pdf](#)
911 Wood S (2020) mgcv: Mixed GAM computation vehicle with automatic smoothness
912 estimation version 1.9-1 from CRAN [WWW Document].
913 <https://rdrr.io/cran/mgcv/> (accessed 10.3.24)
914 Aarts G, MacKenzie M, McConnell B, Fedak M, Matthiopoulos J (2008) Estimating space-
915 use and habitat preference from wildlife telemetry data. *Ecography* 31:140-160
916

917 **Table 1.** Overview of the 12 candidate environmental variables, the spatial resolution of the
918 raster data, and the source of data. Dynamic variables from Copernicus had a temporal
919 resolution of one day. The column “Included in model” indicates whether the variable was
920 included in the final model after accounting for multicollinearity (see section 2.3.2 for
921 details): No=not included in the harbour seal and grey seal models, Yes=included in both
922 harbour seal and grey seal models, Harbour=included in harbour seal model only, and
923 Grey=included in grey seal model only.

Variable	Unit	Spatial		Included in model
		Resolution	Source ^{1,2,3}	
Bathymetry	m	500 m	HELCOM	No
			Calculated from bathymetry data using the R package ‘terra’ (Hijmans et al., 2024)	Yes
Seabed rugosity	m	500 m		
Sediment type	4-class factor	150 m	EMODnet	Yes
Wave exposure	m	250 m	EMODnet	Yes
Current velocity	m/s	1800 m	Copernicus	Yes
Mixed layer thickness	m	1800 m	Copernicus	No
Sea surface salinity	PSU	1800 m	Copernicus	Grey
Surface height	m	1800 m	Copernicus	Harbour
Surface temperature	°C	1800 m	Copernicus	Harbour
Sea-bottom oxygen	mmol/m ³	1800 m	Copernicus	Grey
Sea ice-cover	%	1800 m	Copernicus	No
			Calculated from haulout location data using the R package ‘terra’ (Hijmans et al., 2024)	Yes
Distance from haulout site	km	500 m		

- 924 ¹HELCOM: <https://metadata.helcom.fi/>
- 925 ²EMODnet: <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/>
- 926 ³Copernicus:
- 927 https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/BALTICSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_003_011/

928

929 **Figure 1** Map of the Baltic Sea region with bathymetry and place names used in the text.

930

931 **Figure 2** (A) Tracking data of 90 harbour seals and (B) 65 grey seals colour coded by year of
 932 tagging (released). Black circles highlight locations where individual seals were tagged (size
 933 of the circle is proportional to the number of seals tagged). The dashed lines in B indicate the
 934 spatial extent of the area used by harbour seals in panel A.

935

936

937 **Figure 3** Surveyed haulout locations (in red) and mean annual counts of harbour seals (A,
 938 N=462 haulouts) and grey seals (B, N=841 haulouts) during the period 2000-2024. Circle
 939 size is proportional to the number of seals counted.

940

941

942 **Figure 4** Results of the GAMM analyses showing the predicted mean habitat suitability maps

943 for harbour seals (A) and grey seals (B). Sea areas in white were not included in the model

944 predictions due to environmental dissimilarity (see Methods for details). See Figures S7.1 and

945 S7.2 in Supplementary Material S7 for the predicted lower and upper 95% credible intervals

946 associated with the predicted mean habitat suitability layers for harbour and grey seals,

947 respectively.

948

949

950 **Figure 5** Mean relative population density maps (% at-sea km⁻²) of harbour seals (A) and
 951 grey seals (B). Sea areas in white were not included in the calculations due to environmental
 952 dissimilarity (see text for details). See Figures S7.4 and S7.5 in Supplementary Material S7
 953 for the lower and upper 95% credible intervals associated with the predicted mean relative
 954 population density layers for harbour and grey seals, respectively.

955

956

957

958 **Figure 6** Mean (95% confidence intervals) proportion of overlap (Schoener's D) and
 959 similarity (Warren's I) in habitat suitability and relative population density between harbour
 960 and grey seals in the southwestern Baltic Sea region.

961